

**Supervisor support as a moderator between work schedule flexibility and job stress-
some empirical evidence from Sri Lanka**

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Citation:

Wickramasinghe, V. (2012). Supervisor support as a moderator between work schedule flexibility and job stress: Some empirical evidence from Sri Lanka. International Journal of Workplace Health Management, 5(1), 44-55.

This Version is available at: doi: 10.1108/17538351211215384

Purpose- The purpose of this study was to examine the moderating effect of supervisor support on the relationship between work schedule flexibility and job stress.

Design/methodology/approach- For the study a survey methodology was used and 232 software developers attached to offshore outsourced software development firms responded.

Findings- It was found that supervisor support moderates the relationship between work schedule flexibility and job stress.

Originality/value- It is expected that the findings of this study will provide useful information for both practitioners and academics to better understand the nature of strategies to be adopted in mitigating job stress.

Keywords: supervisor support; work schedule flexibility; job stress; Sri Lanka.

Paper: Research paper

Introduction

There has been a growing recognition of job stress as an important occupational health problem (Antoniou et al., 2003; Johnson et al., 2005). Job stress originates in organisational demands that are experienced by an individual and may be encountered in virtually every key element in the individual's job (Aziz, 2004). Evidence suggests that a higher level of unchecked and unmanaged job stress not only undermines quality, productivity and creativity of employees but also employees' health, well-being and morale, and contributes to a significant portion of worker compensation claims and health-care costs (Antoniou et al., 2003; Burton et al., 2008). Therefore, some of the most important topics of research in people management today revolve around specific policies, practices, programmes, or strategic interventions that appear to influence employee stress (e.g., Anderson et al., 2002; Dooris et al., 2008; Goetzel et al., 2008).

When it comes to addressing stress at the workplace, scholars highlight the need to evaluate different strategies available at the organisational level to find out which strategies

are effective on job stress (see Le Fevre et al., 2006). However, very little evidence is available on which to base the organisational focused stress management strategies and there is little clear information on the relative effectiveness of various strategies in general (see Le Fevre et al., 2006).

In the above context, this paper explores the effects of two contrasting initiatives, i.e., a formal initiative (work schedule flexibility) and an informal initiative (supervisory support) on job stress. Further, scholars have highlighted the need of investigating not only the general effectiveness of strategies but also the importance of investigating moderation effects (see Noblet et al., 2009). Therefore, the specific aim of this paper is to present and discuss the results of an empirical study that investigated the moderating effect of supervisor support on the relationship between work schedule flexibility and job stress.

For the study a random sample of 232 software developers attached to offshore outsourced software development firms in Sri Lanka responded. In this regard, Cooper (2005) suggests that with the process of globalization more and more firms in the West are outsourcing their business work, and the future of work seems to be in outsourced employees in virtual organisations. Further, Tsui (2008, p. 123) suggests that rising prosperity of Asia's growing economies has drawn adverse consequences on employee wellness and the work-life balance of many people. Past research in the context of offshore outsourced software development industry in Sri Lanka provides evidence that work schedule flexibility is offered to software developers as a standard employee benefit (e.g. Wickramasinghe and Jayabandu, 2007). However, the effectiveness of different strategies, specifically, formal (work schedule flexibility) and informal (supervisory support) on job stress in growing sectors like Asian offshore outsourced industry has not yet received due attention. Therefore, it is expected that this paper will provide some useful empirical evidence that could be used in introducing stress management strategies and policies that can make a difference.

In order to provide context for this article, in the next section, relevant literature is briefly reviewed. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main

findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Theoretical background and hypotheses

Job stress

Job stress is generally identified as an adverse reaction people have to excess pressure or demands placed upon them at work. In other words, work-related variables (job stressors), when interpreted by the individual (cognitive interpretation), may lead to stress (Dua, 1994). Therefore, stressors denote the external force or situation acting on the individual - objective events (Le Fevre *et al.*, 2006). A number of aspects of working life have been identified as stressors (see for example Cooper and Marshall, 1976; Voight, 2009; Yang et al., 2008). For instance, role-based factors such as lack of power, role ambiguity, and role conflict (e.g. Nelson and Burke, 2000), threats to career development and achievement such as threat of redundancy, being undervalued, and unclear promotion prospects (e.g. Nelson and Burke, 2000), the quality of the social environment in the workplace including relationships with others (e.g. Cooper and Marshall, 1976), and task uncertainty and task content (e.g. Nelson and Burke, 2000) have been frequently identified as stressors.

The literature suggests that a high level of stress is associated with not only decreased personal health but also impaired individual functioning in the workplace (e.g. Cooper and Marshall, 1976; Stowell et al., 2008). For instance, previous research provides evidence that a high level of stress is associated with decreased capacity to perform, dampened initiative and reduced interest in working, increased rigidity of thought, and a lack of concern for the organisation and colleagues (e.g. Cooper and Marshall, 1976; Dua, 1994; Stowell et al., 2008).

Work schedule flexibility and supervisor support

The literature identifies work schedule flexibility as a form of instrumental support received formally through organisational initiatives to mitigate job stress whereas supervisor support

comes from the immediate supervisor, who can create a more positive work environment (Carlson and Perrewé, 1999; Chen et al., 2009). Therefore, work schedule flexibility and supervisor support can be viewed as two contrasting initiatives, where, work schedule flexibility is a formal policy initiative while supervisor support is an informal initiative. Following sections briefly reviews these two initiatives in relation to job stress.

Work schedule flexibility. The review of literature identifies, on one hand, work schedule flexibility as one of the most prevalent instrumental supports provided by employers (e.g. Almer and Kaplan, 2002; Cohen and Single, 2001; Golden, 2001). On the other hand, the availability of flexible scheduling gives employees greater control over working time, and has been identified by employees as the most cherished management prerogative (Cohen and Single, 2001). Previous research provides evidence that work schedule flexibility reduces job stress (Almer and Kaplan, 2002). For instance, Almer and Kaplan (2002) report that employees in flexible work schedules report lower levels of burnout and stress than those on a standard work arrangement.

Although there are a number of variations in flexible time arrangements, the basic model of flexible time usually consists of five interrelated components: (1) a band within which all hours must be worked (e.g. 6.00 am to 6.30 pm); (2) a core time during which all employees are required to be working (e.g. 10.00 to 12.00 am and 2.00 to 4.00 pm); (3) a flexible band of hours before, after, or in between core times that allows employees to exercise designated options regarding their presence in, or absence from, the work place; (4) banking, which allows a carry-over of surplus or deficient hours worked; and (5) variability of schedule, i.e. the freedom of employees to vary working hours from one period to another without prior approval from their supervisor. Work schedule flexibility is identified as the most frequently utilised and preferred arrangement by employees of the offshore outsourced software development industry in Sri Lanka (Wickramasinghe and Jayabandu, 2007). Wickramasinghe and Jayabandu (2007) report that software developers experience reduction in stress with the implementation of flexible work schedules. Therefore, in this

study, work schedule flexibility is investigated as a form of instrumental support received formally through organisational initiatives, which could impact on job stress experienced by employees. Based on the literature reviewed above that indicates the usage of work schedule flexibility is negatively associated with job stress, for this study, it is proposed that:

Hypothesis 1: The usage of work schedule flexibility will be negatively related to job stress.

Supervisor support. Supervisor support describes the extent to which an employee's supervisor is sensitive to the employee's non-work responsibilities and is willing to accommodate those when conflicting work and non-work demands arise (Carlson and Perrewé, 1999; Mesmer-Magnus and Viswesvaran, 2006). Hence, scholars suggest that supervisor support may make one's work situation less stressful by providing emotional support, instrumental aid or greater control over one's situation (e.g. Anderson et al., 2002; Carlson and Perrewé, 1999). Past researchers further suggested that support from one's supervisor is instrumental in reducing the unfavourable effects of job stress by providing emotional support to increase the stressed individual's self-confidence (e.g. Russell et al., 1987) and self-esteem (e.g. Wong and Cheuk, 2005) by reducing the emotional distress one is experiencing. Likewise, relevant and useful informational support from the supervisor helps the stressed individuals to cope effectively with job-related problems, which in turn reduce the stress one is experiencing (Thomas and Tymon, 1994).

With regard to the treatment of supervisor support in the previous research, several past researchers have shown the effectiveness of supervisor support in buffering the adverse impact of job stress (e.g. Chen et al., 2009; Noblet et al., 2009; Wong and Cheuk, 2005). Therefore, the current study treats supervisor support as a moderator, where supervisor support operates to strengthen the negative relationship between work schedule flexibility and job stress. The hypothesis proposed for this study is:

Hypothesis 2: Supervisor support will moderate the negative relationship between work schedule flexibility and job stress in such a way that job stress will be reduced for higher levels of supervisor support.

Figure 1 shows the hypothesised research model.

Take in Figure I

Methodology

Sample

A random sample of software developers attached full-time to offshore outsourced software development firms was selected. The list of software development firms registered and operate under Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI) was used as BOI is the government authority responsible for identifying, promoting and facilitating export-oriented business operations in the country through both foreign and local investments. Further, it is compulsory by BOI Act (No.4 of 1978) that all BOI registered firms should export at least 90 percent of their output. Therefore, BOI registered software development firms provide at least 90 per cent of their work for offshore client firms. By the end of 2008 there were about 36 firms that were engaged purely in software development. At the second stage, a contact person was identified at each firm. Each contact person was briefed on a one-to-one basis as to the purpose of the study and asked to ensure the anonymity of the respondents and the confidentiality of responses. These contact persons were given the discretion to identify software developers from their firms who were involved in producing information technology (IT) related output as a primary job function. It should be noted that offshore outsourced software development firms typically have two layers in the organisational hierarchy- top management and technical specialists (e.g. Wickramasinghe, 2009). The contact persons

ensured that they had distributed the self-administered survey questionnaire to randomly selected respondents who fell under the category of software development in their firms. Of the 350 questionnaires sent out, 232 valid responses were returned, yielding a response rate of 66% of the original sample. The demographics of the sample are shown in Table I.

Take in Table I

Measures

Independent, dependent and mediator variables were measured using five-point Likert response scales. For all measurement scales, standardised Cronbach's alpha was examined and Principal-components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: Eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair et al., 2006). The items of each factor were averaged to produce a mean score for the each construct (refer to Table II).

Job stress was measured using the five items from Lambert et al., (2006). Example items include "A lot of time my job makes me very frustrated or angry" and "I am usually under a lot of pressure when I am at work". Responses were reported on a 5-point Likert scale from (5) very often to (1) never. The higher value indicates a higher level of job stress. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach's alpha=.858, Eigenvalue=2.64, and explained variation=77.95%.

Supervisor support was measured by the four items from Price (1997). Example items are "My immediate supervisor is willing to listen to my job-related problems" and "My immediate supervisor cares about my well being". Responses were reported on a 5-point Likert scale from (5) strongly agree to (1) strongly disagree. The higher value indicates a

higher level of supervisor support. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach's alpha=.801 Eigenvalue=3.53, and explained variation=75.77%.

The usage of work schedule flexibility was measured by the level of usage of three types of flexible work schedules, namely, periodical flexi time, daily flexi time, and time-offs. These were found to be the most frequently utilised flexible work schedules in the offshore outsourced software development firms in Sri Lanka (Premarathna, 2007). Further, preliminary investigations by the author of the Sri Lankan software development industry revealed that these three options are available in the firms from which the respondents for this study were randomly selected. Periodical flexi time refers to where software developers are allowed to fix their in and out time of a working day for a particular time period (e.g. two weeks). In daily flexi time, software developers are allowed the freedom to change their working hours day-by-day. Time offs are not considered as a leave; software developers are allowed to get time offs during the working hours of a particular day for specific reasons, such as a medical appointment. Therefore, the respondents were asked whether they are allowed to exercise these options regarding their presence in, or absence from, the work place. Three items on a 5-point Likert scale from (5) very often to (1) never were used to derive responses. These items are "How often are you allowed to define the beginning and ending times of your work for a particular time period (e.g. two weeks)", "How often are you allowed to define the beginning and ending times daily basis", and "How often are you allowed to take time offs during the working hours of a particular day for specific reasons, such as a medical appointment". The higher value indicates a higher level of usage of work schedule flexibility. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach's alpha=.717, Eigenvalue=1.93, and explained variation=64.49%.

Literature suggests that individual perceptions may vary by individuals' demographic characteristics (e.g. Antoniou et al., 2003). Therefore, three individual demographic characteristics were controlled in the analysis. These variables are gender (female=0, male=1), marital status (single=0, married=1), and years of experience in the present workplace (in years). Firm size is also included as a control variable. Firm size was

assessed by the natural logarithmic transformation of the number of full-time employees in the organisation.

Data analysis procedure

Hierarchical regression analysis was used to test the moderation hypothesis (see Fraizer et al., 2004). The variables were mean centred to increase interpretability of interactions. The variables were entered into the regression equation in four steps. The control variables were entered in the first step, the independent variable was added in the second step, the moderator variable was added in the third step, and the interaction term was added in the fourth step. The plots were constructed by plotting low, medium and high scores of the variables. For this, Jose's (2002) Excel version of ModGraph programme was used. Following the recommendations of Aiken and West (1991), simple effects tests were conducted to determine whether the slopes differed significantly from zero.

Results

Table II shows means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations among the variables. As can be seen in Table II, work schedule flexibility is negatively associated with job stress. Similarly, supervisor support is negatively associated with job stress. Further, work schedule flexibility and supervisor support are positively related.

Take in Table II

A series of multiple regression analysis were conducted to test the moderator effect of supervisor support. First, control variables were regressed on the outcome variable. The results are shown in Table III (Model 1). Second, the effect of work schedule flexibility on job stress was analysed. As shown in Table III (Model 2), work schedule flexibility is significantly negatively related to job stress. This supports Hypothesis 1. As the third step, supervisor

support was entered into the model. As shown in Table III (Model 3), supervisor support significantly impacts on job stress. Finally, the interaction term was entered into the model to test the moderating effect. Hypothesis 2 predicted that the relationship between work schedule flexibility and job stress would be moderated by supervisor support. As indicated by the significant interaction term in Table III (Model 4), supervisor support moderated the relationship between work schedule flexibility and job stress. Following the recommendations of Aiken and West (1991), simple effects tests were conducted to determine whether the slopes differed significantly from zero. These tests revealed that the relationship between work schedule flexibility and job stress is moderated for medium ($t= 4.91, p<.001$) and high ($t= 3.75, p<.001$) levels of supervisor support and was significantly different from zero.

Take in Table III

Conclusions and implications

The need of attracting and retaining valued employees in a highly competitive labour market has become a strong motivating factor for increased organisational awareness and action with regard to human resource policies and practices to reduce job stress (refer to Coffey et al., 2009). By better understanding effectiveness of formal organisational initiatives and informal support resources, human resource professionals can contribute to the strategic development of policies, practices, and programmes to reduce job stress.

Drawing on previous research, the impact of supervisor support as an informal support resource and work schedule flexibility as a formal policy initiative were examined in reducing negative effects of job stress. As expected when individuals have flexibility in their work schedules they apparently experience less job stress. Similarly, supervisor support was found to be significantly negatively associated with job stress. The results of the regression analysis also supported these claims. These findings support previous research that

reported support from immediate supervisor (e.g. Anderson et al., 2002) and the usage of flexible work scheduling help individuals to reduce stress (e.g. Almer and Kaplan, 2002).

The study investigated whether supervisor support moderates the negative relationship between work schedule flexibility and job stress. As expected, supervisor support is identified as an important resource that serves as a moderator in the negative relationship between work schedule flexibility and job stress. However, the findings suggest that supervisor support moderates the negative relationship between work schedule flexibility and job stress only at medium and high levels of supervisor support. That is low levels of supervisor support may not be effective in strengthening the negative relationship between work schedule flexibility and job stress. Although the calculations of the low, medium and high scores of variables are vital in identifying the moderating effects, these values depend on individual perceptions and in turn how they responded to the survey questionnaire. As discussed in the limitations and future research, individual perceptions may vary from time to time as well as from one sample to another. Therefore, the validity of the measures used in this study and generalizability of the findings cannot be truly established on the basis of a single cross-sectional study. Yet, the findings of the study imply the importance of supportive organisational context created by the immediate supervisor in enhancing the effectiveness of formal work schedule flexibility policies in reducing job stress.

In the current global economic environment, organisations are continually trying to discover value-added initiatives to strategically enhance the performance of their organisations and employees. Therefore, some of the most important topics of research in human resource management revolve around specific policies, practices and programmes that appear to influence employee performance (e.g., Arthur and Cook, 2003). However, some scholars highlight the fact that organisation led initiatives may be intended to serve economic purposes that may be more compelling for the employer than are the needs of their employees (see Arthur and Cook, 2003). As management views have not been pooled in the current study, it is difficult to say whether work schedule flexibility was introduced purely as a stress management strategy. However, the findings of the study imply the

relative significance of informal support from the part of immediate supervisor along with formal work schedule flexibility policies in reducing job stress.

Finally, some limitations of this study, however, should be acknowledged. The sample was confined to a considerably large homogeneous sample of software developers attached to offshore outsourced software development firms that offered three types of work schedule flexibility as a standard employee benefit. However, it should be acknowledged that detailed descriptions of the nature of flexible work schedules that prevail in the firms were not pooled from the respondents, and the availability of the three types of work schedule flexibility was identified by contacting the person responsible for people management in these firms. Hence, the difficulties of describing the sample characteristics by the nature of flexible work schedules have to be acknowledged. If the sample was selected from different industrial and service sectors, findings would have become more generalizable. In this regard, however, literature suggests that the relationships between stress and other factors can differ depending on the group being investigated (e.g. Antoniou et al., 2003). Although organisations could implement a variety of initiatives to help employees to reduce job stress, this study concentrated on one form of such initiatives- work schedule flexibility- as it was the main and most frequently used policy initiative in the industry in Sri Lanka. Further, the study was limited to investigate the moderating effect of supervisor support though there are other forms of social support such as co-worker that could also influence job stress. Finally, the validity of the measures used in this study and generalizability of the findings cannot be truly established on the basis of a single cross-sectional study. The validation of a measure requires the assessment of measurement properties over a variety of samples in similar and different contexts. Hence future research, in different samples and longitudinal studies, are necessary that complement questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data. These all open the door for future investigations.

References

- Aiken, L.S. and West, S.G. (1991), *Multiple Regression: Testing and Interpreting Interactions*. Sage, Thousand Oaks, CA
- Almer, E.D. and Kaplan, S.E. (2002), "The effects of flexible work arrangements on stressors, burnout, and behavioral job outcomes in public accounting", *Behavioral Research in Accounting*, Vol. 14, pp. 1-34.
- Anderson, S.E., Coffey, B.S. and Byerly, R.T. (2002), "Formal organizational initiatives and informal workplace practices: links to work–family conflict and job-related outcomes", *Journal of Management*, Vol. 28 No. 6, pp. 787–810.
- Antoniou, A-S.G., Davidson, M.J. and Cooper, C.L. (2003), "Occupational stress, job satisfaction and health state in male and female junior hospital doctors in Greece", *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, Vol. 18 No.6, pp. 592-621.
- Arthur, M.M. and Cook, A. (2003), "The relationship between work–family human resource practices and firm profitability: a multi-theoretical perspective", *Research in Personnel and Human Resources Management*, Vol. 22, pp. 219-252.
- Aziz, M. (2004). "Role stress among women in the Indian information technology sector", *Women in Management Review*, Vol. 19 No. 7, pp.356-363.
- Burton, W.N., Schultz, A.B., Chen, C-Y. and Edington, D.W. (2008), "The association of worker productivity and mental health: a review of the literature", *International Journal of Workplace Health Management*, Vol. 1 No. 2, pp. 78-94.
- Carlson, D.S. and Perrewé, P.L. (1999), "The role of social support in the stressor-strain relationship: an examination of work-family conflict", *Journal of Management*, Vol. 25 No. 4, pp. 513–540.
- Chen, W-Q., Siu, O-L., Lu, J-F., Cooper, C.L. and Phillips, D.R. (2009), "Work stress and depression: the direct and moderating effects of informal social support and coping", *Stress and Health*, Vol. 25 No. 5, pp. 431-443.

Coffey, M., Dugdill, L. and Tattersall, A. (2009), "Designing a stress management intervention in social services", *International Journal of Workplace Health Management*, Vol. 2 No. 2, pp. 98-114.

Cohen, J.R. and Single, L.E. (2001), "An examination of the perceived impact of flexible work arrangements on professional opportunities in public accounting", *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol. 32 No. 4, pp. 317-328.

Cooper, C.L. (2005), "The future of work: careers, stress and well-being", *Career Development International*, Vol. 10 No. 5, pp.396-399.

Cooper, C.L. and Marshall, J. (1976), "Occupational sources of stress: a review of the literature relating to coronary heart disease and mental ill health", *Journal of occupational psychology*, Vol. 49 No. 1, 11-28.

Cousins, R., MacKay, C.J., Clarke, S.D., Kelly, C., Kelly, P.J. and McCaig, R.H. (2004), "Management standards' and work-related stress in the UK: practical development", *Work and Stress*, Vol. 18 No. 2, pp. 113-136.

Dooris, M., Sedgley, L. and Dugdill, L. (2008), "A reflective analysis of the development of a regional workplace health strategy in the North West of England", *International Journal of Workplace Health Management*, Vol. 1 No. 3, pp. 209-218.

Dua, J.K. (1994), "Job stressors and their effects on physical health, emotional health, and job satisfaction in a university. *Journal of Educational Administration*, Vol. 32 No. 1, pp. 59-78.

Frazier, P.A., Tix, A.P. Barron, K.E. (2004), "Testing moderator and mediator in counseling psychology", *Journal of Counseling Psychology* Vol. 51 No. 1, pp. 115-134.

Goetzel, R.Z., Ozminkowski, R.J., Bowen, J. and Tabrizi, M.J. (2008), "Employer integration of health promotion and health protection programs" *International Journal of Workplace Health Management*, Vol. 1 No. 2, pp.109-122.

Golden, L. (2001), "Flexible work time: correlates and consequences of work scheduling – flexible work schedules, which workers get them?", *The American Behavioral Scientist*, Vol. 44 No. 7, pp. 1157-1178.

Hair, J.F.Jr, Black, W.C., Babin, B.J., Anderson, R.E. and Tatham, R.L. (2006), *Multivariate Data Analysis*, 6th Ed. India: Pearson Education.

Johnson, S., Cooper, C., Cartwright, S., Donald, I., Taylor, P. and Millet, C. (2005), "The experience of work-related stress across occupations" *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, Vol. 20 No. 2, pp. 178–187.

Jose, P.E., (2002), *ModGraph - A computer programme to graphically display moderation*.
Online at: http://www.victoria.ac.nz/psyc/staff/paul-jose/files/helpcentre/help1_intro.php

Lambert, E.G., Hogan, N.L., Camp, S.D. and Ventura, L.A. (2006), "The impact of work–family conflict on correctional staff: a preliminary study", *Criminology and Criminal Justice*, Vol. 6 No. 4, pp. 371-387.

Le Fevre, M., Kolt, G.S. and Matheny, J. (2006), "Eustress, distress and their interpretation in primary and secondary occupational stress management interventions: which way first?", *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, Vol. 21 No. 6, pp. 547-565.

Mesmer-Magnus, J.R. and Viswesvaran, C. (2006), "How family-friendly work environments affect work/family conflict: a meta-analytic examination", *Journal of Labor Research*, XXVII, Vol. 4 No. 4, 555-574.

Nelson, D.L. and Burke, R.J. (2000), 'Women executives: health, stress, and success', *Academy of Management Executive*, Vol. 14 No. 2, pp. 107-121.

Noblet, A., Rodwell, J. and Allisey, A. (2009), "Job stress in the law enforcement sector: comparing the linear, non-linear and interaction effects of working conditions", *Stress and Health*, Vol. 25, pp. 111–120.

Pierce, J.L. and Newstrom, J.W. (1983), "The design of flexible work schedules and employee responses: relationships and processes", *Journal of Occupational Behavior*, Vol. 4 No. 4, pp. 247-62.

Premarathna, U.P.S.P. (2007), An investigation of work-life balance among software engineers, Unpublished MBA dissertation, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

Price, J.L. (1997), "Handbook of organizational measurement", *International Journal of Manpower*, Vol. 18 No. 4/5/6, pp. 305-558.

Russell, D.W., Altmaier, E. and Van Velzen, D. (1987), "Job-related stress, social support, and burnout among classroom teachers", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 72 No. 2, pp. 269-274.

Stowell, J.R., Tumminaro, T. and Attarwala, M. (2008), "Moderating effects of coping on the relationship between test anxiety and negative mood", *Stress and Health*, Vol. 24 No. 4, pp. 313-321.

Thomas, K.W. and Tymon, W.G. (1994), "Does empowerment always work? Understanding the role of intrinsic motivation and personal interpretation", *Journal of Management Systems*, Vol. 6 No. 3, pp. 1-13.

Tsui, A.H.H. (2008), "Asian wellness in decline: a cost of rising prosperity", *International Journal of Workplace Health Management*, Vol. 1 No. 2, pp. 123-135.

Voight, M. (2009), "Sources of stress and coping strategies of US soccer officials", *Stress and Health*, Vol. 25 No. 1, pp. 91-101.

Wickramasinghe, V. (2009), "Predictors of job satisfaction among IT graduates in offshore outsourced IT firms", *Personnel Review*, Vol. 38 No. 4, pp. 413-431.

Wickramasinghe, V. and Jayabandu, S. (2007), "Towards workplace flexibility: flexitime arrangements in Sri Lanka", *Employee Relations*, Vol. 29 No. 6, pp. 554-575.

Wong, K.S. and Cheuk, W.H. (2005), "Job-related stress and social support in kindergarten principals: the case of Macau", *International Journal of Educational Management*, Vol. 19 No. 3, pp. 183-196.

Yang, L-Q., Che, H. and Spector, P.E. (2008), "Job stress and well-being: an examination from the view of person–environment fit," *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, Vol. 81, pp. 567–587.

Tables

Table I: Sample description

Sex:	
Male	66%
Female	44%
Marital status:	
Single	47%
Married	53%
The highest level of qualification:	
Bachelor's degree or equivalent professional qualifications [†]	83%
Postgraduate degree [‡]	17%
Age:	
Mean	30 years
S.D.	2.86
Minimum	27 years
Maximum	40 years
Availability of dependents:	
Yes	82%
No	18%
Tenure in the present firm:	
Mean	3 years
S.D.	1.55
Minimum	11 months
Maximum	7 years
Number of full-time employees in the present workplace:	
Mean	350
Minimum	45
Maximum	4000
Tenure in the IT industry :	
Mean	7 years
S.D.	1.94
Minimum	11 months
Maximum	11 years

Notes: N=119

S.D.= standard deviation

[†] Membership in British Computer Society, Australian Computer Society, and Project Management Professional.

[‡] M.Sc. in information Technology, M.Sc. in Computer Science, and Master of Business Administration (MBA) specialised in Information Technology, MBA specialised in Management of Technology, and MBA (general).

Table II: Means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6
1 Gender	.62	.49	1					
2 Marital status	.27	.44	-.042	1				
3 Tenure	3.35	1.55	.112	.263**	1			
4 No. of employees	5.81	1.22	-.134	.090	.079	1		
5 Work schedule flexibility	3.59	.59	.185*	.026	.132	.071	1	
6 Supervisor support	3.66	.75	-.027	.104	.115	.036	.212*	1
7 Job stress	3.82	.74	-.154	.059	.054	-.066	-.245*	-.349**

Note: * significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

** significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Table III: Results of hierarchical regression analysis

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
<i>Step 1: Control:</i>				
Gender	-.157	-.187	-.165	-.166
Marital status	.079	.072	.099	.063
Tenure	.065	.039	.048	.026
No. of employees	-.099	-.087	-.125	-.093
<i>Step 2: Independent:</i>				
Work schedule flexibility		-.188**	-.170**	-.220*
<i>Step 3: Moderator:</i>				
Supervisor support			-.357***	-.346***
<i>Step 4: Interaction term:</i>				
Work schedule flexibility x Supervisor support				-.251**
R ² (Adj.)	.021	.165	.184	.213
F change	.909	1.317**	3.229***	3.296***

Note: * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<.001.

Figure

Figure I: Hypothesised research model